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ABSTRACTS

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OP-038

In-silico molecular docking, ADMET analysis, and toxicity prediction for investigating insecticidal activity of *Curcuma angustifolia* essential oil against *Lasioderma serricorne*: a severe insect pest in stored coriander seeds

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Abstract: Coriander seeds, derived from the *Coriandrum sativum* plant, are used as a culinary spice and offer several health benefits. These are rich in nutrients and a good source of vitamins and antioxidants. *Lasioderma serricorne* is the major insect pest species that infest and damage the stored coriander seeds. Their larvae feed on the inner contents of the seeds, leaving behind frass and silk webbing. Synthetic insecticides like DEET, chlorpyrifos, and trichlorfon damage the ecological balance. Essential oil-based insecticides getting more popular nowadays. These green insecticides are safer to use and easily decompose in the environment. The present research work focused on the computation docking and the prediction of natural insecticidal agents from CAEO against the targeted AChE (Acetylcholinesterase) of *L. serricorne*. Major bioactive compounds of CAEO were achieved by Gas chromatography–mass spectrometry. Out of 72 compounds, only 7 bioactive compounds were present in major amounts. Eucalyptol (14.35%), Vulgarone (11.67%) followed by Germacrone (7.93%), Linalool (5.06%), Camphor (3.82%) and A-pinene (3.58%). Homology modeling of the targeted protein was done via Phyre2 and validation was done by Ramachandran plot. DogSiteScorer was used to predict the active site. Ligands were downloaded from PubChem. Molecular docking was performed by AutoDockVina and protein ligand interaction was seen in Discovery Studio. The binding affinity and docking score of vulgarone was more excellent than the standard compound (DEET). ADMET analysis and toxicity prediction of the best-docked ligand were checked by Swiss ADME and ProToII to understand the pharmacophore kinetics and the acute toxicity.

Keywords: Essential oil, Molecular docking, AChE, ADMET, ProToxII.

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